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**OUTSTANDING GEORGIAN WRITERS AND PUBLIC FIGURES
OF THE 19TH CENTURY ABOUT ADJARA**

Summary. The fall of Samtskhe-saatabago, one of the most advanced parts of old Georgia, was caused by the capture of Konstantinopol by the Turks (May 1453, 29) and the fact that they became neighbors of Georgia. Georgia was culturally separated from the European educational centers. There was a decrease in trade as well. In 1461, the capture of the Trapezus empire by the Turks created a great danger to Samtskhe-saatabago and Guria. Constant attacks from Turks on Samtskhe-saatabago land began.

Politically fragmented and weakened Georgia fought against the invaders for almost a century and a half, and in this battle the enemy was defeated many times, but domestic political disagreements between the Georgian Kingdoms, enmity between individual principalities contributed to the fulfilment of the conquerors' intentions. At the end of the 16th century, Turkish domination was established in old Meskheta or Samtskhe-saatabago, the part of which Adjara was. In the Kura and Chorokhi Gorges, Turkish domination destroyed Georgian cultural centers: monasteries and schools, where the old Georgian cultural heritage was preserved.

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In the 18-10s of the 10th century, the territory of present-day Adjara fell completely into the hands of Turkish invaders. The life of the adjarians in the hands of the Turks was hard and unbearable. In the harem and slavery, Adjarian women were heard. Sons of Adjarian were made into slaves and Janissaries and the Muslim faith was abandoned in this beautiful corner of Meskheta.

Georgian intellectuals, intimidated by the policy of Turkish Barbarians, did not dare to travel to this area. Not only Georgian intellectuals, but also Europeans did not dare to travel to Ajara, this is confirmed by the book "travel to Georgia" by French traveler Jean Chardin, which describes the predation of Turkish conquerors, which could not overcome the 1672 rule of Gonio. Shardeni, robbed and insulted, addressed the Turkish abuser in this way: "nobody will come to gonio if they find out that they treat travelers with such violence and so unfairly here" (Shardeni, 1935, p. 47).

Sulkhan-Saba orbekiani also describes the barbarism of the Turkish conqueror, as it is known, a wonderful Georgian writer and statesman Sulkhan-Saba orbekiani traveled to France on a diplomatic mission in 1714 and kept Ludovico fourteenth. Upon returning to his homeland, Sulkhan-Saba Orbekiani traveled through Chaneti to Gonio. In Chania, they inflicted unspeakable pain on him: "they caught us, consumed us a lot, took away twenty marchers, broke

zandukas... Customs Service was used in vain and many people were in trouble" writes Saba (Orbeliani, 1940, p. 149).

After a hard ordeal, the great writer barely redeemed himself from Turkish pirates and went beyond the coast of gonio.

Famous Georgian writer and playwright Giorgi Eristavi, who visited Batumi during his trip to Europe in 1862, writes: "You have long looked at the small Kariba town of Batumi. The house is like a house... Go into thoughts "(Eristavi, 1936, p. 332).

It was quite rightly noted by Alexander Froneli: "those who have not lived in Islamized Georgia cannot imagine the sadness and heart murmur that the Muslim Georgian audience, who came from the middle of Georgia, feels" (Froneli, 1914, p. 20).

It was necessary for every Georgian to turn thinking about Adjara into a practical activity, and indeed, the revival of this case begins in the 70s of the 19th century. Letters about South Georgia, namely Adjara, were systematically placed on the pages of the newspapers of that time.

After Giorgi Eristavi, the ravaged Adjara was first kept by Niko Nikoladze, who wrote an extensive letter about Adjara in 1873 in the 4th "collection" with the title "by the way". N. Nikoladze's review is important because the Georgian writing of the 19th century first raised his voice with his pen due to the deplorable state of Adjara in the hands of the conquering Turks. The letter feels the feelings and heartache of the advanced Georgian intelligentsia. He argues that the Turkish invaders took this once prosperous part of Georgia on the path of economically and culturally decline.

Tedo Sakhokia rightly wrote: "a man should get to know Adjarian close to truly appreciate his chivalrous character. If you show a good heart, you bet for yourself, you will consider this mountain child blessed. But if there is also one bit, it is merciless to give you light" (Sakhokia, 1950, p. 109).

Ilia Chavchavadze was most familiar with the Raider character of the conquered Georgians-adjarians, because in this corner they completely retained all the valiant habits of the Amber warrior. As far as I knew well, Chavchavadze in this corner of Meskheta was so heartless.

Ilia Chavchavadze had high hopes for the Russian-Turkish War of 1877–1878. He believed that he would positively solve the issue of removing South Georgia from the Turks. Ilia gathered the Advanced children of Georgia around him, who were actively working and were exploring the path of an extremely important common case. Ilia Chavchavadze hoped that the adjarians would keep their native, Georgian language and morals intact.

Famous public figure Petre Umikashvili was interested in studying South Georgia. He traveled all over South Georgia to get acquainted with the living conditions of the then Muslim Georgians. Umikashvili compares adjarians to mountaineers and writes: "adjarians with morality are strong, they love toffee hooting and guns. Respect, hospitality, self-control, curiosity are the first qualities of adjarians" (Gaz. "Iveria" 1877: N15)

At the cost of the great sacrifice, the historical injustice was partially corrected, and Ajara joined Mother-Georgia. There was joy throughout the country. The Georgian Press met the release of Adjara with great celebration. The newspapers of that time wrote with great news about this joyful and historical fact.

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